

1 Supporting Information for:

2 **Sorption of ionic liquids in soil enriched with polystyrene microplastic reveals independent**
3 **behavior of cations and anions.**

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Figure S1. Freundlich's isotherms for [Chol] cation.

1% PS OECD OECD + 1% PS

2% PS OECD OECD + 2% PS

5% PS OECD OECD + 5% PS

10% PS OECD OECD + 10% PS

Figure S2. Freundlich's isotherms for [C₁₂Chol] cation

Table S1. Coefficients 1/n and K_f calculated for [Chol] cation for all tested systems

System	Simple linear regression model	R^2	1/n	K_f [$\text{mg}^{1-1/n} \text{L}^{1/n}/\text{g}$]
1% PS	$y = 0.994x + 0.0069$	0.9992	0.994	1.02 ± 0.07
2% PS	$y = 0.9583x + 0.014$	0.9982	0.9583	1.03 ± 0.06
5% PS	$y = 0.9677x + 0.0516$	0.9994	0.9677	1.13 ± 0.09
10% PS	$y = 1.0193x + 0.0251$	0.9991	1.0193	1.06 ± 0.08
OECD	$y = 1.0078x + 0.583$	1	1.0078	3.83 ± 0.25
OECD + 1% PS	$y = 1.0228x + 0.6184$	0.9999	1.0228	4.15 ± 0.28
OECD + 2% PS	$y = 1.0145x + 0.6381$	0.9998	1.0145	4.35 ± 0.30
OECD + 5% PS	$y = 1.0186x + 0.6029$	0.9998	1.0186	4.01 ± 0.22
OECD + 10% PS	$y = 1.0285x + 0.6403$	0.9998	1.0285	4.37 ± 0.31

Table S2. Coefficients 1/n and K_f calculated for [C_{12}Chol] cation for all tested systems

System	Simple linear regression model	R^2	1/n	K_f [$\text{mg}^{1-1/n} \text{L}^{1/n}/\text{g}$]
1% PS	$y = 0.9584x + 0.1401$	0.9885	0.9584	1.38 ± 0.09
2% PS	$y = 1.0063x + 0.1163$	1	1.0063	1.31 ± 0.08
5% PS	$y = 1.0121x + 0.118$	0.9997	1.0121	1.31 ± 0.08
10% PS	$y = 1.1762x + 0.2232$	0.9997	1.1762	1.67 ± 0.10
OECD	$y = 1.2676x + 2.4486$	0.9948	1.2676	280.91 ± 14.34
OECD + 1% PS	$y = 0.6724x + 2.5513$	0.9941	0.6724	355.71 ± 35.79
OECD + 2% PS	$y = 0.7004x + 2.5898$	0.9887	0.7004	388.87 ± 37.41
OECD + 5% PS	$y = 0.6853x + 2.5801$	0.9969	0.6853	380.28 ± 33.81
OECD + 10% PS	$y = 0.5539x + 2.504$	0.9994	0.5539	319.15 ± 25.28